

Assessment of Broadcast Media's Adherence to NBC Code in Promoting Equitable Agribusiness and Sustainable Farming Practices in Ibadan

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Abstract

This study examined the adherence of broadcast media to the Nigerian Broadcasting Commission (NBC) Code in promoting equitable agribusiness and sustainable farming in Ibadan, Nigeria. Stemming from the Social Responsibility theory that the media must provide necessary information to serve the public, this study also identified the prevalent themes and content of the stations' agribusiness-related programmes, investigated farmers' perceptions of the programmes' effectiveness, and identified the challenges and likely solutions for the stations in this regard. This study adopted a mixed-methods design, using content analysis on agricultural programmes of three radio stations: Premier FM (Federal), Oluyole FM (State), and Lagelu FM (Private), between January and June 2025, with a survey of 292 farmers and interviews with 15 radio staff and 5 NBC officials. Lagelu FM has the highest 60% adherence to the NBC Code in promoting agribusiness, followed by Premier FM (32%) and Oluyole FM (30%). While Lagelu FM's agribusiness-related programmes focused on floriculture (40%) and agribusiness and marketing (20%), Premier FM's *Agbe-Asejere* and Oluyole FM's *Boluyo* concentrated on crop cultivation (40% and 35% respectively) and livestock farming (30% and 25% respectively). The farmers perceived Lagelu FM's programmes more effective (40%) than its public counterparts. The challenges included the non-inclusion of a specific agricultural section in the NBC Code and inadequate funding, among others. Although adherence to the NBC Code is uneven among the stations, the radio's role remains crucial for equitable agribusiness and sustainable farming practices in Ibadan. The NBC should create a specific section for agriculture-related programmes and enforce guidelines, while stations should seek partnerships to address challenges.

Keywords: Agribusiness, NBC Code, Radio, Social Responsibility Theory, Sustainable Farming.

Word Count: 260

Background to the Study

The agricultural sector is a cornerstone of the Nigerian economy, contributing over 40% to the country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and playing a crucial role in ensuring national food security, providing employment, and driving growth (Zainab & Oluwadamilare, 2024). Despite its foundational importance, the sector faces significant challenges, including low technology adoption, inadequate infrastructure, climate variability, and limited access to finance and modern farming techniques (Asak, Eke & Adeyemi, 2025). Addressing these issues is crucial for achieving sustainable development and improving the livelihoods of the millions of smallholder farmers who make up a large portion of the farming population.

According to Ogunniyi and Ojebuyi (2016), agribusiness encompasses a wide range of activities, such as harvesting and transportation of crops like maize and cassava to the storage and preservation of farm products like livestock and fish. It also involves the sale of these products, often requiring specialised expertise, like skilled butchers at slaughterhouses. Additionally, agribusiness includes animal husbandry, where farmers raise livestock like goats, sheep, and cows to meet the meat demands of both rural and urban communities, and the production of essential commodities like honey, dairy products, and fresh produce, which cater to household needs and serve various purposes (Ogunniyi & Ojebuyi, 2016).

In this context, effective communication is vital for disseminating new farming techniques, market information, and government policies to rural farmers (Adebayo & Olaniyan, 2021a). Mass media affordability and broad reach make them indispensable for farmers in rural communities who may lack access to electricity, television, or the internet (Kumar & Vijayakumar, cited by Darji & Yadav, 2024). The use of indigenous languages in radio broadcasts is especially effective, as it greatly improves comprehension and influences farmers' knowledge and behavioural change, ultimately boosting their productivity (Adebayo & Olaniyan, 2021a; Asak *et al*, 2025).

According to Olatunji, Sanyaolu and Akin-Morakinyo (2024), the Nigerian government, through its regulatory bodies, actively works to safeguard and promote the nation's interests in the media sector. Established to regulate the industry, the National Broadcasting Commission (NBC) ensures compliance and maintains standards among broadcast media outlets (Michael, 2025). The Commission oversees broadcast content to ensure it aligns with public interests and supports the nation's growth across social, cultural, and economic domains (NBC, 2019). It does this by

prohibiting any broadcasting medium whose content is not beneficial to the public (Onebunne & Okeke, 2020).

To carry out its statutory functions effectively, NBC put in place a broadcasting code to set standards in the area of content and quality of material for broadcasting. This document outlines guidelines for broadcasting in Nigeria, serving as a reference for industry best practices (Ihechu, Ebenezer & Saviour, 2022). The NBC Code outlines these objectives, providing a framework that guides all broadcast activities, including promoting Nigerian indigenous cultures and community life (Asak *et al*, 2025). While this Code provides a clear mandate for public service, the extent to which stations of different ownership models – Federal, State, and private – adhere to these provisions, particularly concerning the niche area of agribusiness and sustainable farming, remains a critical area for scholarly assessment.

Statement of the Problem

Scholars have drawn attention to the agricultural sector from various perspectives. Some researchers, particularly in Nigeria, have explored the potential of digital tools, including mobile phones, to enhance agricultural productivity and market efficiency (Olowu & Oyedokun, 2000; Falola & Adewumi, 2011; Idrisa, Ogunbameru & Shehu, 2013; Ogunniyi & Ojebuyi, 2016; Mane, 2024). In the context of the media and agricultural sector, Jabeen and Gul (2023) evaluated the role of social media in promoting sustainable agriculture practices, while Asak *et al* (2025) explored how broadcast media evaluate government initiatives in Nigeria's agricultural sector, particularly after significant policy shifts.

From the foregoing, there is a notable lack of scholarly research on the media's role in promoting equitable agribusiness and sustainable farming practices, particularly regarding the media's compliance with the NBC code in fulfilling this social responsibility function; this is the gap that this study aims to fill. Therefore, this current study, focusing on radio stations in Ibadan, aims to assess broadcast media's adherence to the NBC code in promoting equitable agribusiness and sustainable farming practices.

Research Questions

In line with the objectives, this study seeks to answer the following research questions:

1. To what extent do broadcast radio stations in Ibadan adhere to the NBC Code in their agricultural programming?
2. What are the prevalent themes and content of agribusiness and farming-related programmes in the selected stations?
3. How do farmers perceive the effectiveness of agricultural programming on the radio stations on their agribusiness and farming practices in Ibadan?
4. What are the challenges and likely solutions for Ibadan radio stations in promoting agribusiness and sustainable farming?

Broadcast Media's Role in Promoting Agribusiness and Sustainable Farming

Broadcast media, particularly radio, serve as a critical platform for disseminating agricultural policies and providing real-time updates on market trends and technological innovations to farmers (Olayemi, 2022). The accessibility of radio, especially in Nigeria's rural communities, makes it an essential medium for sharing information on government strategies and modern farming techniques, such as climate-smart agriculture (Asak *et al*, 2025). The integration of indigenous languages in radio broadcasts is a key factor that enhances farmers' comprehension and ensures that vital information reaches diverse communities (Olayemi, 2022; Asak *et al*, 2025). Examples like the Kilimo Hai program in Kenya and Farmer Voice Radio across Sub-Saharan Africa demonstrate successful models where radio bridges the gap between researchers and farmers, providing knowledge on ecologically sustainable agriculture and improving livelihoods (Asak *et al*, 2025).

Despite this crucial role, the effectiveness of Nigerian broadcast media is significantly challenged by systemic issues. A central finding is the media's over-reliance on government narratives and press releases, which limits its ability to provide comprehensive and balanced information (Asak *et al*, 2025). This over-reliance often results in a focus on policy promotion rather than critical analysis or in-depth policy evaluation (Olayemi, 2022). There is a documented lack of investigative journalism and on-the-ground reporting, which means critical challenges

faced by farmers may remain underreported (Olayemi, 2022; Asak *et al*, 2025). This scenario creates a paradox of proximity, where the medium is physically accessible via a radio set.

However, the content itself is distant from the reality of the farmer's experience due to its heavy reliance on official sources rather than direct engagement with stakeholders (Olayemi, 2022). Such a one-way flow of information undermines the participatory communication that is so successful in other contexts (Fact and Reports 2017) and risks creating a disconnect between government strategies and their actual implementation. Political interference and regulatory constraints further compound this issue, hindering media organisations from providing the objective analysis necessary to ensure transparency and accountability in the agricultural sector (Olayemi, 2022; Asak *et al*, 2025).

The Nexus of Media, Agriculture, and Sustainable Development

The connection between media and agricultural development is well-established in academic literature. Radio, in particular, has been identified as an indispensable tool for bridging the information gap faced by rural farmers (Albany, 2012). Studies have shown that radio can successfully instruct rural dwellers on cultivation, animal farming, and other farming techniques, thereby influencing their practices and helping them adopt new knowledge and skills (Adebayo & Olaniyan, 2021a). The effectiveness of this medium is significantly amplified when programmes are broadcast in indigenous languages, which enhances farmers' comprehension and can be correlated with an increase in productivity (Adebayo & Olaniyan, 2021a). For instance, a study in North-Central Nigeria found that agricultural radio programmes in indigenous languages significantly influenced farmers' knowledge, acceptance, and behavioural change, ultimately boosting their productivity (Adebayo & Olaniyan, 2021b).

Beyond its instructional role, radio serves as a crucial platform for disseminating market trends, weather forecasts, and government policies (Asak *et al*, 2025). It provides a mechanism for stakeholders – farmers, policymakers, and agricultural experts – to engage in dialogue, ensuring that policies are well-understood and adapted to local contexts. This role aligns with the principles of development communication, which emphasises using media to drive socio-economic progress (Suleiman, 2022).

National Broadcasting Commission (NBC) Code for Broadcast Media in Promoting Agriculture and Sustainable Farming Practices

The National Broadcasting Commission (NBC) was established by Decree 38 of 1992, subsequently amended by Act 55 of 1999 (NBC Decree, 1992; NBC Act 1999). The NBC is the central regulatory body for broadcast media, established to guide all stations in what and how to carry out broadcasting (Asak *et al*, 2025). The Code's principles are in line with the nation's fundamental objectives, aiming to provide enlightenment, promote social values, and contribute to the social, cultural, and economic development of the country (JMC Study Hub, 2025). Its primary responsibility is to regulate and control the broadcasting industry in Nigeria (NBC, 2019). Succinctly stated by Chukwuma (2025:6):

The National Broadcasting Commission (NBC) oversees broadcasting in Nigeria, handling tasks such as licensing and regulating radio, television, and cable TV services, direct satellite broadcast, and so on; regulating and controlling the broadcasting industry; receiving, considering and investigating complaints from individuals and bodies regarding content of a broadcast or conduct of a station; upholding the principles of equity and fairness in broadcasting; establishing and disseminating a national broadcasting code and setting standards with regards to contents and quality of broadcasting; regulating ethical standard and technical excellence; promoting Nigerian indigenous cultures, moral and community life through broadcasting; determining and applying sanctions, including revocation of licences of defaulting stations; ensuring quality manpower development in the broadcasting industry by accrediting curricula and programmes for all tertiary institutions that offer Mass Communication in relation to broadcasting; and intervening and arbitrating in conflicts in the broadcasting industry.

Media regulation involves formal guidelines that shape the activities of media organisations. In Nigeria, the National Broadcasting Commission plays a crucial role in ensuring that broadcast media contribute significantly to the country's development across various spheres (Olatunji *et al*, 2024). The broadcast media, therefore, have the responsibility to provide fair representation to smallholder farmers, policymakers, agricultural experts, and extension workers. It also implies that media content should not be skewed to favour one type of farming practice over another, ensuring that both traditional and modern techniques are discussed (Olayemi, 2022; Asak

et al, 2025). An equitable approach would also require broadcasters to critically examine the economic and social impact of agricultural policies rather than simply promoting them without scrutiny.

The NBC's goal of showcasing Nigeria's rich cultural heritage can be applied to agricultural broadcasting, highlighting the country's farming traditions and community values. As agriculture is a central component of community life and cultural identity in many parts of Nigeria, including Ibadan's surrounding areas, broadcasting on farming issues in indigenous languages is a direct and meaningful way for stations to fulfil this mandate. The success of models like Simli Radio, which uses vernacular languages to communicate directly with farmers, demonstrates the power of this approach (Fact and Reports, 2017).

Adherence, in this context, is measured by the degree to which a radio station's agricultural programming critically examines policy rather than just promoting it; features diverse voices beyond government officials; provides balanced information on equitable agribusiness and sustainable practices; and considers the long-term environmental and social impacts of farming. These guidelines are embedded in Section 3.14, sub-sections 2a and 2b of the NBC Code (NBC Code, 2019, p.64).

However, the implementation and enforcement of the Code have faced scrutiny. Research suggests that while the NBC has been effective in regulating political and religious content, its enforcement of cultural and sports broadcasting codes has been inadequate (Asak *et al*, 2025). This observation implies a potential systemic issue where developmental and cultural content, including agriculture, may not be prioritised. This issue poses a challenge for media houses and reinforces the need for a more comprehensive assessment of their adherence to their developmental mandates (Asak *et al*, 2025).

Theoretical Framework

The Social Responsibility Theory frames this study as a crucial framework that places the ethical burden of serving the public interest on media practitioners themselves (Skana & Gjerazi, 2024). A balanced approach to media freedom and regulation is crucial in developing nations like Nigeria, where the media plays a vital role in driving progress. Key principles of this approach include prioritising accuracy, fairness, and contributing positively to society (Asak *et al*, 2025).

Nevertheless, critics of this theory note that media houses may prioritise content that attracts affluent demographics for advertising revenue, potentially neglecting the issues of marginalised groups, such as rural farmers (Skana & Gjerazi, 2024). When ideals are not put into practice, there is a disconnect between what is expected and the actual outcome. Evaluating whether radio stations truly serve the broad public interest in their agricultural programming, or whether commercial pressures shape their content, is therefore central to this analysis.

Methodology

The population of this study included the radio stations only in Ibadan, Oyo State, and the staff members of the radio stations. Also, involved were the farmers in Ibadan, and the staff members of the National Broadcasting Commission (NBC), Ibadan.

The study employed a mixed-method research design combining both the quantitative and qualitative methods of data gathering. The quantitative approach involved Content Analysis (for research questions 1 and 2) and the Survey method (for research question 3), while the qualitative approach involved an in-depth interview (for research question 4).

Therefore, various sampling techniques were used. For the radio stations, the stratified sampling technique was used to categorise the 42 radio stations in Ibadan into Federal-owned, State-owned, and privately-owned. A Random sampling technique was used to select one radio station from each category, namely: Premier FM 93.5, Oluyole FM 98.5 and Lagelu FM 96.7 accordingly. This selection was used for the Content Analysis, such that the selected radio stations' agriculture-related programmes were analysed for six months from January to June 2025. Meanwhile, an inter-coder reliability test was conducted to ensure the trustworthiness and objectivity of the Content Analysis to assess the agreement between the two coders; hence, the resulting coefficient of 0.85 was achieved, which is above the generally accepted threshold of 0.70, confirming the reliability of the coding procedure.

For the Survey, the stratified sampling technique was again used to categorise the 11 local government areas in Ibadan into urban, semi-urban and rural areas. Then, a simple random technique was also used to select one local government from each category, namely: Egbeda, Lagelu and Akinyele accordingly. Furthermore, a convenience sampling technique was used to select 100 farmers from each selected local government, making a total of 300 sampled farmers.

For the in-depth interview, five staff members were selected from each selected radio stations, making 15 radio staff, and five NBC staff members were also interviewed.

In total, the sample size for this study was three radio stations (Premier FM 93.5, Oluyole FM 98.5 and Lagelu FM 96.7) whose programmes were content analysed, and 300 sampled farmers for the survey. Also, there were 15 radio staff and 5 NBC staff for the interview.

Therefore, the research instruments used to gather data for this study were content categories and coding sheets for the Content Analysis method, a questionnaire for the Survey method, and the interview guide for the in-depth interview method. Also, it should be stated that questionnaire copies were administered to 300 farmers, but 292 were retrieved and analysed using frequency count and simple percentages.

Before data collection, ethical rigour was ensured through informed consent, whereby all participants (staff and farmers) were fully apprised of the study's purpose and their right to voluntary participation and withdrawal. Also, strict measures guaranteeing anonymity and confidentiality were implemented.

Data Analysis and Findings

Research Question 1: To what extent do broadcast radio stations in Ibadan adhere to the NBC Code in their agricultural programming?

To answer this, a scoring system was developed based on key provisions of the NBC Code relevant to public service broadcasting and developmental content. Adherence percentage was measured using variables such as the percentage of airtime dedicated to agricultural content and the degree of objectivity. This was done by dividing the Total Observed Compliance Score achieved by the radio station across all criteria by the Total Possible Compliance Score, and then multiplying the result by 100.

Table 1: Radio Stations’ Adherence to NBC Code in broadcast of Agric-related Programmes

Radio Stations	Name of Programme	% Airtime on Agriculture	Average Adherence (%)
Premier FM (Fed.)	<i>Agbe-Asejere</i> (Prosperous Farming)	10%	32%
Oluyole FM (State)	<i>Boluyo</i> (Feeding the Nation)	10%	30%
Lagelu FM (Private)	Various programmes via NIHORT: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biopesticides • Embracing Sustainable Agriculture • Agric-friendly Environment • Floriculture 	35%	60%

Source: Content Analysis 2025

The data in Table 1 above indicate a clear difference in adherence to the NBC Code based on station ownership. Premier FM (Federal) has one agribusiness-related programme known as *Agbe-Asejere* (Prosperous Farming) sponsored by the Institute of Agricultural Research and Training (IAR&T) with 10% airing time and 35% adherence to the NBC Code. Similarly, Oluyole FM (State) has one agribusiness-related programme called *Boluyo* (Feeding the Nation) with 10% airing time apiece and 30% adherence. Notably, Lagelu FM (Private) demonstrated a higher adherence (60%) with a higher focus on agricultural programming (35%), having numerous agribusiness-related programmes in collaboration with the National Horticultural Research Institute (NIHORT), which include Biopesticides, Promoting Cut Flower Production, Embracing Sustainable Agriculture, and Agric-friendly Environment. This suggests that private stations are more concerned with the developmental mandates outlined in the NBC Code and use indigenous languages more than their public counterparts.

Research Question 2: What are the prevalent themes and content of agribusiness and farming-related programmes at the selected stations?

The agribusiness and farming contents were categorised as follows: Crop Cultivation, Livestock Farming, Agribusiness & Marketing, Government Policies, Flower Cultivation, and Weather

Forecasts. Also, the dominant programme format common across all stations was a talk show or interview with experts.

Table 2: Prevalent Themes/Content of the Stations' Agribusiness-related Programmes

Themes/Contents	Premier FM	Oluyole FM	Lagelu FM
Crop Cultivation	40%	35%	15%
Livestock Farming	30%	25%	5%
Agribusiness & Marketing	10%	10%	20%
Government Policies	15%	10%	5%
Flower Cultivation	-	-	40%
Weather Forecasts	5%	10%	15%

Source: Content Analysis 2025

The data in Table 2 above show a divergence in content focus. Premier FM, on its *Agbe-Asejere* programme, focuses on crop cultivation (40%) and livestock farming (30%); as well as Oluyole FM's *Boluyo* programme, which also concentrates on crop farming and livestock cultivation (35% and 25% respectively). In contrast, Lagelu FM allocates a larger portion of its airtime to floriculture (40%), agribusiness and marketing (20%), and crop cultivation (15%), as well as weather forecasts (15%). This indicates that private stations prioritise agribusiness-related content more than their public counterparts.

Research Question 3: How do farmers perceive the effectiveness of agricultural programming on the radio stations on their agribusiness and farming practices in Ibadan?

The total sampled farmers who were administered the questionnaire was 292. The questionnaire was designed to elicit information from the farmers on the effectiveness of the stations' agric-related programmes in promoting equitable agribusiness and sustainable farming practices among them.

Figure 1: Farmers' Perception of Programmes' Effectiveness in Promoting Agribusiness
Source: Survey 2025

The survey results strongly align with the findings of the content analysis. Farmers perceived the programmes on Lagelu FM as significantly more effective (40%) than those of Premier FM (32%) and Oluyole FM (28%). The high scores suggest that farmers find the content of Lagelu FM credible and useful for their farming practices. These also indicate that the farming community consider radio agribusiness-related programming as a reliable source of information for their agricultural practices.

Research Question 4: What are the challenges and likely solutions for Ibadan radio stations in promoting agribusiness and sustainable farming?

The in-depth interviews with 15 radio staff (5 from each station) and 5 NBC staff provided crucial qualitative insights to address key challenges influencing the broadcast of agricultural content. The majority of the radio staff expressed that the major challenge is the non-specific section for agricultural content in the NBC Code, which, according to many of them, makes it difficult to determine exactly what the radio stations expect to package in their agric-related programming. One staff member expressed that:

The NBC is like the broadcasting Bible, it contains sections on almost every aspect of broadcasting, such as Children and Youth, Sports, News and Current Affairs,

Religion, Politics, Advertisement and Commercials, Music and others; but there is none for agriculture. Something about agriculture only reflects under the Sub-section for Economic Objectives, where it is stated that the broadcasting shall ensure consistency with the nation's economic goals. Be current with the trends and developments in production processes, promote knowledge of available products and services through programmes and advertisements, foster the spirit of hard work and productivity to improve the quality of life of the people, and encourage the production and consumption of local products to achieve self-sufficiency and self-reliance. No specific section or sub-section is dedicated to Agriculture in the NBC Code, which seems as if even the NBC does not see agriculture broadcasting as important, hence its omission from the Code.

Another key challenge identified by most of the farmers was inadequate funding and sponsorship of agriculture-related programmes. One of them specifically stated that, "agricultural programmes do not generate significant revenue, which is why it is difficult to justify dedicated airtime." Another radio staff member said, "There are fewer radio adverts from entrepreneurs of agro-related business on agriculture programmes, while some who had subscribed could not sustain the subscription for many months."

Also, the majority of the respondents opined that another key challenge in the broadcast of agriculture-related programmes is the lack of specialised staff. "There is generally a shortage of journalists with specialised knowledge in agriculture," a radio staff member said. An NBC official corroborated this, that, "many stations lack dedicated agriculture desks because they don't have agricultural specialist broadcasters."

Meanwhile, concerning the likely solutions to the challenges identified, most of the radio staff acknowledged that there should be partnerships with agricultural research institutes (like NIHORT, IITA and IAR&T), government agencies (like the Ministry of Agriculture), and agribusiness firms. According to a broadcaster, "Partnering with an agricultural institute and agency is like using a stone to kill three birds, because it will solve about three challenges – it will provide specialised expertise for broadcasting, a steady stream of content, and help to mitigate the financial challenges."

In addition, another identified likely solution by the broadcasters was social media integration. An NBC staff member suggested that “the use of social media and podcasts to complement radio broadcasts in this situation is essential and cannot be undermined.” Supporting this view, a radio staff member said, “The use of social media will allow for visual content, interactive sessions, and a wider reach beyond traditional radio signals.”

Discussion of Research Findings

The findings of this study reveal a significant disparity in the quality and focus of agricultural broadcasting across different ownership models in Ibadan. The data from content analysis and surveys consistently show that the privately-owned radio stations have stronger adherence to the developmental mandates of the NBC Code towards agribusiness-related issues than both the Federal and State radio stations.

The low adherence to the NBC Code by public stations (Premier FM and Oluyole FM) is highly significant, challenging their core public service mandate under the Social Responsibility theory. This underperformance not only marginalises essential information for the farming community but also exposes a deep regulatory and accountability paradox where enforcement against state-owned media proves difficult. Ultimately, this deficiency stems from systemic issues like inadequate funding and a lack of specialised expertise, highlighting that sustained improvement requires a policy focus on overcoming these fundamental institutional weaknesses rather than just addressing non-compliance.

Nevertheless, all the radio programmes are rich in practical farming techniques, and they are perceived by farmers as effective in promoting their agribusiness and farming practices to a large extent. This aligns with the Social Responsibility Theory, where the media is expected to serve a public purpose, especially in developmental contexts (Skana & Gjerazi, 2024; Asak *et al*, 2025). The in-depth interviews with staff from the private stations corroborated this, affirming their commitment to society.

Importantly, it was found that non-inclusion of a dedicated section for agricultural content in the NBC Code is a major challenge to broadcasting agric-related programmes. Other challenges identified are inadequate funding, lack of sponsorship and specialised expertise. Nevertheless, a major likely solution is a mutual partnership between broadcast stations and agricultural institutions/agencies, which will help mitigate all the challenges to a large extent.

Overall, the findings of the study affirm that the broadcast media's role in promoting agribusiness and rural development is crucial and cannot be underestimated (Ogunniyi & Ojebuyi, 2016; Olayemi, 2022; Asak *et al*, 2025). In addition, the findings indicate that while the NBC Code provides a clear framework for public interest broadcasting (Olatunji *et al*, 2024), its adherence is uneven among the broadcast media.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study concludes that there is a significant discrepancy in the adherence to the NBC Code among different radio stations in Ibadan, particularly concerning the promotion of equitable agribusiness and sustainable farming. Nevertheless, radio broadcasting is crucial for equitable agribusiness and sustainable farming practices in Ibadan.

This research makes a critical contribution by providing empirical evidence distinguishing between the rhetoric and the reality of media performance under different ownership models in a developmental context. Specifically, it advances the understanding of the Social Responsibility theory in practice by quantifying how private broadcasters can surpass public stations in fulfilling regulatory developmental mandates. Also, this study uniquely identifies the institutional barriers (lack of funding, expertise) and regulatory lacunae (non-inclusion of a specific agricultural section in the NBC Code) that directly impede the effectiveness of public service media in supporting rural development, offering a granular basis for future policy review regarding media accountability and sustainability in specialised sectors.

Based on the findings and conclusions of this study, the following are recommended:

1. **For the National Broadcasting Commission (NBC):** The NBC should create a specific section for agriculture-related programmes and develop more specific guidelines to enforce adherence among broadcast stations to meeting their public service obligations, particularly in critical sectors like agriculture. Also, the Commission could create a reward system or grant programmes to incentivise stations to produce high-quality, relevant agricultural programming.
2. **For Broadcast Stations:** Broadcast stations should re-evaluate their Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) by dedicating more airtime to agricultural programmes as a way of giving back to their host communities and fulfilling their developmental role. Also, these

stations should actively seek collaborations with agricultural bodies, NGOs, and government agencies. These partnerships could provide funding, expertise, and a steady stream of content, helping to mitigate the financial challenges.

3. **For Farmers and Agricultural Stakeholders:** Farmers' associations should engage with radio stations and the NBC to advocate for more programming that directly addresses their needs, from farming techniques to market access. This could include organising listening groups and providing feedback to station managers.

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